

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for tryptophan metabolite analysis of dried blood spots (DBS) via LC-QQQ

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Summary

Gut microbiota is an important factor affecting human health. The tryptophan metabolites (anthranilate, indole-3-acetamide, indole-3-acetate, indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-butyric acid, indole-3-lactic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan, *N*-acetyl tryptophan) perform important signalling and immunomodulatory functions, especially interaction of the innate immune system of the host with PXR or AHR xenobiotic receptors. This protocol describe preparation of dried blood spots (DBS) and quantitative/semiquantitative determination using LC-QQQ. Sample preparation of DBS is complementary to the protein analysis and thus allows the simultaneous determination of tryptophan metabolites and proteins in DBS.

Preparation

Safety information

- Dried blood spots are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- Isopropanol: flammable liquids, eye irritation, specific target organ toxicity following single exposure

Equipment

- 10 μ L multichannel, 250 μ L multichannel pipettes & 1 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates
- pH meter

Consumables & glassware

- 40 mL screw cap plastic vials
- 4 mL screw cap glass vial and cap
- 500 μ L 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 150 μ L 96-well PCR plates with silicone sealing
- 10 μ L, 250 μ L & 1 mL tips

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

- DBS on paper
- Scissors for DBS samples
- DBS stored in -80 °C freezer and thawed at room temperature
- 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer (40 mg/10 mL in milliQ)
- For 20 mL of solution, weigh 80 mg ammonium bicarbonate buffer into 40 mL screw plastic vial
- Add 20 mL of milliQ
- Solution should have pH = 7.8 (measure with pH meter)
 - Solution can be kept for 7 days at 4 °C temperature

Labeled standard mix:

[¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful, irritating

[²H₅] L-kynurenine (99 % isotope enrichment)

[¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan (99 % isotope enrichment)

[²H₅] [¹⁵N] indole-3-acetamide (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

[¹³C₆] anthranilate (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

Indolmix (native standard mix) each = 250 nM in 25% (v/v) isopropanol

indol-3-acetic acid –harmful, irritating

L-kynurenine

L-tryptophan

indol-3-acetamide - harmful

anthranilate - harmful

N-acetyl-tryptophan – harmful, irritating

Indol-3-aldehyde - irritating

Indol-3-butyric acid - Toxic if swallowed, irritation

Indol-3-lactic acid - irritating

Indol-3-propionic acid - irritating

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- Acetonitrile, LC-MS grade
- Formic acid (FA), LC-MS grade
- MilliQ water

Procedure

Standard preparation

1. Prepare 1.5 mL aliquot of 2000 nM [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid, 2000 nM L-kynurenine [²H₅], 20000 nM L-tryptophan [¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂], 50 nM indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N], 200 nM anthranilate [¹³C₆] in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
2. Pipette directly or dry the internal reference standard mix down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in -80 °C and reconstitute in the solvent before analysis

Sample preparation

1. NOTE: Store DBS samples at -80 °C
2. Take out DBS from freezer and leave at room temperature for 20 min
3. Cut the 3 mm spots from DBS paper (Scissors for DBS samples)
4. Place 2 DBS into 500 µL 96-well plate and pipette 150 µL ammonium bicarbonate buffer (use multichannel pipette)
5. Place onto the shaker and shake for 60 min (200 RPM at room temperature)
6. Dry the rest of the sample (containing DBS) in Centrifugal evaporator
7. To dry sample add 400 µL of 80% (v/v) isopropanol and vortex for 20 min (200 RPM at room temperature)
8. Centrifuge the samples 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)
9. Pipette 300 µL of the supernatant to 150 µL 96-well PCR plates and dry in Centrifugal evaporator (dry extracts can be stored in -80 °C) (use multichannel pipettes)
10. Redissolve in 10 µL 5% (v/v) isopropanol standard mix containing: 200 nM [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate, 2000 nM [²H₅]L-kynurenine, 20000 nM L-tryptophan [¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂], 50 nM indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N], 200 nM anthranilate [¹³C₆] (use multichannel pipettes)

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water (solution can be kept for 7 days at 4 °C temperature)

- Mobile phase B: 0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile

NOTE: use at least 5% milliQ water in acetonitrile (prevent LC clogging)

LC-QQQ analysis

3. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
4. Check solvent for needle rinsing
5. Check solvent for seals rinsing
6. Prepare mobile phase
7. Input sequence
8. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
9. Check initial blanks, standard mix = Indolmix, Labelled standard mix and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- Procedural blank (same preparation as samples; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC (pool of samples extract; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC dilution series in 3 replicates (same sample preparation as QC with 2x, 4x, 8x dilution & spiked with Labelled standard mix)
- Indolmix
- Labelled standard mix in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of DBS extract → spike Labelled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)
- QC_dilution series in 3 replicates (dilute QC: 2x, 4x, 8x & spike with same concentration of Labelled standard mix)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

1. Clean_blank
2. Clean_blank
3. Instrument blank
4. Indolmix
5. Indolmix
6. Indolmix
7. Labelled standard mix
8. QC_dilution series
9. Procedural blank
10. QC sample
11. Samples 1-3
12. Instrument blank
13. Sample 4-6
14. Instrument blank
15. Sample 7-9 ...

NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: measure Indolmix with every 30 samples

NOTE: measure Labelled standard mix minimum 3 times (at the beginning of the batch, in the middle of the batch and the end of the batch)

16. Calibration
17. End with Indolmix, Instrument blank and 2 x Clean blank

Table 1. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

COMPOUND	PRECURSOR	PRODUCT	RT [MIN]
L-KYNURENINE*	209.09	192.00	1.6
L-KYNURENINE	209.09	94.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE*	215.13	198.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE	215.13	96.10	1.6
L-TRYPTOPHAN *	205.10	188.00	2.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN	205.10	91.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN*	218.10	200.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN	218.10	98.10	2.9
ANTHRANILIC ACID	138.06	120.00	7.2
ANTHRANILIC ACID*	138.06	65.00	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID	144.08	126.10	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID*	144.08	70.20	7.2
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	175.09	130.07	7.3
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	175.09	103.00	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	181.12	134.10	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	181.12	106.00	7.3
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN*	247.11	188.10	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	130.00	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	118.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	188.00	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	130.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTID ACID*	206.06	117.90	7.8
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE*	146.06	118.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	117.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	91.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	65.10	8.0

INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	39.20	8.0
INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	176.07	130.07	8.2
[¹³ C ₆] INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	182.10	136.10	8.2
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID*	190.09	130.07	8.6
INDOLE-3-PROPIONIC ACID	190.09	55.06	8.6
INDOL-3-BURYTIC ACID*	204.10	186.08	8.9
INDOL-3-BURYTIC ACID	204.10	168.00	8.9

* *Transition used for quantification*

SRM metabolite quantitative/semi-quantitative evaluation

1. For concentration determination of indole-3-acetic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan, anthranilate and indol-3-acetamide use internal standardization with isotopically labelled standards [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate, [²D₄] *L*-kynurenine, [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] *L*-tryptophan, [¹³C₆] anthranilate and indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N]

The calculation is based on the concentration of isotopically labelled standard added to DBS sample, measured response (integrated peak area) of isotopically labelled standard, and response (integrated peak area) of metabolite Equation (1).

$$c_{met} = \left(\frac{CIS}{AIS} \times A_{met} \right) (1)$$

2. For the lack of commercially available standards, the concentration of indole-3-propionic, indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic, indol-3-butyric acid and N-acetyl tryptophan are determined with response factor (RF) Equation (2).

NOTE: use [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate as a *C_{IS}*

$$c_{met} = \left(\frac{CIS}{AIS} \times A_{met} \right) : RF (2)$$

RF are calculated from Indolmix and Labelled standard mix determined in Equation (3)

$$RF = \left(\frac{A_{met}}{AIS} \times \frac{CIS}{C_{met}} \right) (3)$$

NOTE: no normalization used

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler settings

Injection volume			2 μ L
Needle Wash			Multi-wash
Stoptime			As Pump/No Limit
Posttime			Off
Advanced	Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 μ L/min
		Eject Speed	100 μ L/min
		Wait time After Draw	0 s
	Needle Height position	Offset	-0.4 mm
		Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
	High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out factor	5.0
		Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
		Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump

Flow	0.3 mL/min		
Solvents	A:	0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water	
	B:	0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile	
Pressure limits	Min	0 bar	
	Max	1200 bar	
Stoptime	14 min		
Posttime	Off		
Advanced: Timetable	Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]
	0	95	5
	5	90	10
	10	5	95
	11.99	5	95
	12.00	95	5
	14.00	95	5

Column comp

Temperature	40 °C		
Advanced	Enable analysis	When temperature is within	\pm 0.8 °C

QQQ

Source parameters	Gas Temp:	160 °C
	Gas Flow:	15 L/min
	Nebulizer:	25 psi
	Sheath Gas Temp:	250 °C
	Sheath Gas Flow:	12 L/min

iFunnel parameters	Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)
	Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
	High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
	Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)
Chromatogram	Stop Time		
	No limit/As Pump		
Time segments	Ion source	AJS ESI	
	Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min
	Start Time	Scan type	Div Valve
	1	0	MRM
2	10.5	MRM	To Waste

Column & guard column: Acquity UHPLC CSHTM C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) & VanGuard ACQUITY UPLC CSH C18 (5 x 2.1 mm; 1.7 μm) from Waters